

high with a 3:1 ratio. Golden snail meat meal can safely replace fish or meat meal in food animal diets.

Shell meal was Ca-rich, with 35.05% Ca. It could potentially replace oyster shell meal.

Table 2 shows average production performance of growing/finishing pigs fed GSM-supplemented diets. The response criteria—average daily gain, average daily feed consumption, and average feed conversion efficiency—

showed insignificant differences across treatments.

The results indicate GSM could be used as a feed supplement for growing/finishing pigs. □

Loss of rice grain yield and seedling vigor due to sheath rot (ShR) and mealy bug interaction

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We observed a severe ShR *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams and Hawksw. outbreak in Sep-Oct 1990 in IR20 ricefields infected with mealy bug *Brevinnia rehi* Lindinger.

The flag leaf of individual tillers was assessed and tagged with waterproof color tape according to ShR severity at grain maturity stage. The *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) was

used. About 100 samples, replicated five times, represented each severity class.

Mealy bugs inside ShR-infected sheaths were counted for each class. Panicles within seventy classes were bulked, dried separately. Thousand-grain weight and percent of healthy, discolored, and chaffy grains were recorded.

We evaluated seedling vigor after storage for 1 mo at room temperature with a standard test. Fifty seeds were incubated between double-layer blotter paper in 9-cm plates for 2 wk at 25°C with four replications per sample. We recorded the number of germinated seeds, and shoot and root lengths after 2 wk.

ShR severity was positively correlated ($r = 0.99^{**}$) with mealy bug population (see figure). Their interaction greatly reduced 1,000-grain weight, grain yield (9-77%), and healthy grains percentage; it increased chaffy and discolored grains.

Correlation of sheath rot severity and mealy bug population Sep-Oct 1990 at ACRI.

Seed germination and root length were significantly reduced, but shoot length was not. □

Water management

Water use by irrigated summer rice

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We measured use of water by summer rice through evapotranspiration and deep percolation. Soils were medium black, clay loam texture, pH 6.9, 0.82% organic C, infiltration rate 1.0-1.5 cm/h.

The technique used two 200-liter capacity leakproof drums, 60 cm in diameter and 90 cm high. One drum had

an open bottom; the second, a closed bottom. The drums were installed in oversized pits 60 cm deep and 65 cm in diameter in the ricefield, leaving about 30 cm of the drum height aboveground. The soil was backfilled layerwise and compacted to approximately the same bulk density as that of the surrounding soil.

Mean evapotranspiration use and deep percolation loss at different growth phases of summer rice.^a Maharashtra, India, 1987-89.

	Water use (mm)									
	Open-bottom drum					Closed-bottom drum				
	Transplanting to maximum tillering	Maximum tillering to flowering	Flowering to milk stage	Milk to maturity	Total (90 d)	Transplanting to maximum tillering	Maximum tillering to flowering	Flowering to milk stage	Milk to maturity	Total (90 d)
Total evapotranspiration + deep percolation	528.3	678.9	342.0	450.4	1999.6	280.8	372.9	203.9	271.0	1128.5
Average/d	21.1	22.6	22.8	22.5	-	11.2	12.4	13.6	13.6	-
Through evapotranspiration	-	-	-	-	-	280.8	372.9	203.9	271.0	1128.5
Through deep percolation	247.5	306.0	138.2	179.4	871.1	-	-	-	-	-
Deep percolation/d	9.9	10.2	9.2	8.9	-	-	-	-	-	-
Percolation (%)	46.9	45.1	40.4	39.8	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aAv for 3 yr.

At transplanting, the surface soil in each drum was brought to the same puddled condition as that of the surrounding field. Water use in the open-bottom drum constituted evapotranspiration and deep percolation; water use in the closed-bottom drum constituted evapotranspiration alone.

Seedlings of rice variety Ratna were transplanted in mid-Jan. A 5-cm water level was maintained by refilling with a measured quantity of water. There was no rainfall during the growing season,

The highest water use through evapotranspiration (732.9 mm) and deep

percolation occurred from tillering to flowering (see table). Of a total 1999.5 mm water used by the crop, 56.4% met evapotranspiration needs; 43.5% was lost through deep percolation. □

Water balance in banded ricefields under different rainfed situations in Central India

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The Chhattisgarh region of Central India grows about 5 million ha of rice, 20% irrigated, the rest rainfed. Soil variability ranges from lateritic to clay to sandy loam and clay loam.

We examined the climatic water balance under banded field condition in three major riceland soils. We computed excessive, normal, and deficit rainfall situations for four stations using the Thornthwaite and Mather (1955) book-keeping procedure.

Rainfall and potential evapotranspiration values were used to obtain soil moisture storage, actual evapotranspiration, water deficit, and water surplus. We assumed that runoff occurred only with more than 10 cm standing water in banded ricefields, and percolation losses are always higher than runoff losses.

The two water losses were estimated under water surplus conditions in the water balance computations. The amount of water at field capacity was assumed to be 150 mm for sandy loam, 200 mm for clay loam, and 250 mm for clay soils, up to 1-m depth.

For annual rainfall data, three rainfall patterns were worked out for 1901-1987: excessive (greater than mean [MI + standard deviation [SD]], normal (M + SD to M - SD), and deficit (less than M - SD).

The probability of excessive rainfall pattern occurrence at the four stations ranged from 8 to 17%; that of normal

Water balance of different districts.

Parameter (mm)	Sandy loam (Matasi)			Clay loam (Dorsa)			Clay soils (Kanhar)		
	Excessive	Normal	Deficit	Excessive	Normal	Deficit	Excessive	Normal	Deficit
<i>Raipur</i>									
Rainfall	1813.5	1142.2	763.2	1813.5	1142.2	763.2	1813.2	1142.2	763.2
Percolation	1032.6	434.9	137.1	730.8	389.6	76.1	220.2	312.6	26.3
Runoff	85.1	0	0	262.9	0	0	398.3	27.2	0
<i>Rajnandgaon</i>									
Rainfall	2002.3	1232.2	682.4	2002.3	1232.2	682.4	2002.3	1232.2	682.4
Percolation	958.0	535.8	59.2	850.7	475.8	8.3	621.6	405.7	0
Runoff	75.2	0	0	323.1	10.0	0	724.1	29.7	0
<i>Durg</i>									
Rainfall	1736.5	1136.7	862.7	1736.7	1136.7	862.7	1736.9	1136.7	862.7
Percolation	981.2	450.5	244.8	390.5	390.5	193.8	580.5	314.8	137.6
Runoff	0	0	0	0	0	0	375.7	24.8	6.2
<i>Bilaspur</i>									
Rainfall	1475.6	1201.0	804.3	1475.6	1201.0	804.3	1475.6	1201.0	804.3
Percolation	970.9	462.1	153.2	499.4	390.1	103.2	399.4	348.3	52.7
Runoff	18.5	0	0	143.8	22.0	0	244.4	13.9	0

Annual rainfall (mm)

